

Consent information for the interviewees

Interview: What is the Impact of Varying Requirements Quality on QAs, developers, and requirements engineers and their work?

The purpose of this form is to inform you about our project on the Impact of Requirements Quality on QAs, developers, and requirements engineers and highlight the features of your participation in this study.

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1 Who is running this study?

The study is being conducted by a master thesis student at the Department of Software Engineering (DIPT) at Blekinge Institute of Technology.

2 What is the purpose of this study?

The study aims at identifying the observable effects of varying requirements quality and its consequences for QAs, developers, and requirements engineers. To do so, we wish to conduct interviews with quality assurance employees, newly employed developers, and requirements engineers at the organization to identify “golden-standard” requirements that are considered “good quality”- and “smelly requirements” that are considered “bad quality”. We also aim to identify the observable effect of the varying requirements qualities.

4 Who will have access to my responses and data?

After the session, you will be given a unique identifier, which we will use when we transcribe your responses. We will also record the interview to help with the transcription, and any record will only exist as local files not available to anyone outside the responsible for this study. This anonymizes your data and ensures that only we know the names of the participants. The key to your identifier will be kept in a password-protected document.

Once we finish the transcription and analysis process, the records will be destroyed together with all the traces between your identity and the data used in the analysis. The anonymized entries and analysis will only be seen by us. The results from the analysis might be published in scientific venues, but the data will be presented in an anonymous form, and we will ensure that any information that might make you directly identifiable is **not** included. All data will be handled in accordance with strict ethical practices.

5 Do I have to do this?

Your participation is completely voluntary. You can withdraw from the study at any point without giving a reason, and if requested, all the data regarding your participation (including the transcriptions of the interview) will be destroyed.

6 Can I ask questions?

Before the study begins, we will make sure you understand the study and what you need to do. Please feel free to ask us any questions you may have about the study process, either during the introduction of the session or at any time during the study.

After the end of the study, we would like to hear from you about your experiences of participating in this study. This can be done either in person, through the phone or email, to answer any final questions you might have and for us to clarify anything that was not clear in any of your interventions in the invention. We will contact you after the session to see if you are willing to do this.

7 Keeping participants well and healthy

It is very unlikely that participating in this study will trigger any unpleasant thoughts or feelings. However, if this does occur, we advise you to consult us as soon as possible.